

Calibration Weights and Standard Error Estimate for the Quarterly Tax Survey (Q-Tax)

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Abstract

The U.S. Census Bureau conducts the Quarterly Summary of State and Local Government Tax Revenue Survey (Q-Tax). This paper describes a calibration-weighting method for the local, state, local non-property, and corporate income taxes. Standard error estimates for the Q-Tax calibration estimator are provided using a generalized linear regression GREG (Deville and Särndal 1992). Compared to the current calibration procedure using SUDAAN, test results show the proposed codes using R raking proportional fitting and GREG regression yield estimates with smaller coefficients of variation for Q-Tax T09, T40, and T41 survey data from 2020 Quarter 1 to 2023 Quarter 2.

Key Words: Calibration Weighting, WTADJUST, SUDAAN, Raking, GREG

1. Introduction

In Public Sector surveys, sample units are selected using a sample design which produces a set of weights associated with sampled units. The design weights account for unequal probabilities of selection, nonresponse, and other factors affecting imbalance between the population and the sample. These weights can be used to produce design-based estimation such as the Horvitz-Thompson (HT) estimator of the population total. For a study variable $Y = (y_1, \dots, y_N)$ and a set of auxiliary variables X , our parameter of interest is the population total $t_y = y_1 + \dots + y_N$ where N is the population size. The HT estimator $\hat{t}_{yHT} = d_1 y_1 + \dots + d_n y_n$ where $d_i = 1/\pi_i$ is the design weight, π_i is the first order inclusion probability for unit i , and n is the sample size. The HT estimator is design-unbiased where the weights are independent to the survey sample. When the population total of the auxiliary variables X are known, $t_x = x_1 + \dots + x_N$, the calibration estimator (Deville and Särndal 1992) $\hat{t}_{yCAL} = w_1 y_1 + \dots + w_n y_n$, where the distance between calibrated weight (w_1, \dots, w_n) and the design weight (d_1, \dots, d_n) is minimized under the calibration equations $t_x = w_1 x_1 + \dots + w_n x_n$. The calibration estimator \hat{t}_{yCAL} is no longer design-unbiased for t_y . However, the bias is small, and the mean squared error is smaller than the design-based HT estimator. An early algorithm to produce weight calibration by Deming and Stephen (1940) is the raking ratio algorithm. The algorithm consists of an outer cycle that checks convergence criteria and an inner cycle that iterates over the control variables.

In this paper, Q-Tax survey data is described in Section 2, then in Section 3 we describe the current calibration procedure in production using SUDAAN at the Public Sector Sample Design and Estimation Branch (PSSDEB). Section 4 provides standard error estimates for the Q-Tax calibration estimator using Deville and Särndal (1992) variance estimator as applied to the raking proportional fitting and a generalized linear regression (GREG). Compared to the current calibration procedure using SUDAAN, test results show the proposed codes using R raking proportional fitting and GREG regression yield estimates with smaller coefficients of variation for Q-Tax T09, T40, and T41 survey data from 2020 Quarter 1 through 2023 Quarter 2. Test results are provided in Section 5.

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Each calibration estimation (from 2020Q1 through 2023Q2 for Q-Tax T09, T40, and T41) including estimation, standard error estimate (SE) and coefficient of variation (CV) of the estimates can be found from Tables in the appendix.

2. Q-Tax and ALFIN data

Q-Tax comprises three tax components: local government property tax (F-71), state government tax (F-72), and local government revenue from non-property taxes (F-73). The PSSDEB creates a sample design for F-73: the quarterly survey of selected Non-Property Taxes that collects data on local government revenue from non-property taxes. The F-73 survey provides quarterly estimates for the national totals and consists of (1) T09: General sales and gross receipts tax (T09), (2) T40: Individual income tax (T40) and (3) T41: Corporate net income tax (T41). Our sample in this study contains these three variables and auxiliary information such as assets, debt, revenue, expenditures, 2017 and 2022 Census of Governments values for T09, T40 and T41 are available to us. The sample design is a stratified πps design (Särndal et al., 1992). The final sample size is 1,800 and there are 14,015 local governments in the sampling frame. A detailed overview of Q-Tax sample design can be found in Dumbacher and Hogue (2014).

The Annual Survey of State and Local Government Finances (ALFIN), or Local Finance, collects tax data annually. A calibration of Q-Tax to ALFIN is performed to make the Q-Tax estimation totals for the four quarters in a calendar year agree with the ALFIN total.

More information about the Q-Tax and ALFIN data can be found at <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/ntax/technical-documentation/methodology.html> and <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/gov-finances.html> respectively.

3. Current Q-Tax Estimation Procedure

As an example of the current Q-Tax estimation procedure, this section describes the estimation for 2023 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 1.

Step 1: Select Q-Tax and ALFIN data (prior to the current year 2023) to set up the calibration equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i^{yearQT} &= u^{yearALFIN} \text{ for } year = 2017, \dots, 2021 \text{ and } n = 1423 \\ \sum_{i=1}^n w_i &= N \text{ where } N = 9032 \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: Use the calibration weights to estimate the total Q-Tax for 2023 T09 Q1 as

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i^{2023T09Q1}$$

A SUDAAN procedure is used to produce calibrated weights, Q-Tax estimate, and its standard error estimation.

4. Calibration Weighting Methods and Variance Estimation

Calibration weights are computed by minimizing a distance measure between the calibrated weights and the design weights (Deville and Särndal 1992). The simplest distance measure for calibration is the chi-square distance:

$$\chi^2(w, d) = \sum_{i=1}^n (w_i - d_i)^2 / (q_i d_i)$$

where q_i is a pre-specified constant and is called q-factor and $1/q_i$ is the positive weight unrelated to the design weight d_i .

4.1 Raking calibration

The raking (iterative proportional fitting) calibration, an early algorithm to perform weight calibration, is often attributed to Deming and Stephan (1940) who developed the sampling techniques that were used for the first time during the 1940 U.S. Census. In a simple 2-variable example the marginal totals are known from the entire population, but the joint distribution of the two variables is known only from a weighted sample arranged in rows and columns. Sample row totals are proportionally adjusted to conform to the population row totals. Then the column totals are proportionally adjusted to conform to the population column totals, and so on until convergence is reached. See Deville and Särndal (1992) and Kolenikov (2014) for a version of a raking algorithm.

4.2 Linear calibration (GREG estimator)

The GREG estimator assumes a linear relation between the variable of interest (current year Q-Tax) denoted by y and the auxiliary variable (prior years Q-Tax) denoted by x

$$\hat{t}_{GREG} = \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{y}_i + \sum_{i=1}^n d_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)$$

$$\hat{y}_i = (\mathbf{x}_i)' \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}},$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} = [\sum_{k=1}^n d_k q_k \mathbf{x}_k (\mathbf{x}_k)']^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^n d_k q_k \mathbf{x}_k y_k$.

Let d_i be a design weight, and w_i be a calibrated weight w_i . Then

$$\hat{t}_{GREG} = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i g_i y_i = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i y_i$$

where g_i is the adjusted weight factor of the design weight d_i . The adjusted weight factor does not depend on \mathbf{y} and is given by

$$g_i = 1 + \left(\sum_{k=1}^n w_k x_k - \sum_{k=1}^n d_k x_k \right)' \left(\sum_{k=1}^n d_k q_k \mathbf{x}_k (\mathbf{x}_k)' \right)^{-1} q_i x_i$$

where q_i is a scale factor depending on auxiliary data x_i chosen to take account for heteroscedasticity. In general, q_i can be a function of one of the covariates in the regression model.

Any calibration estimator is asymptotically equivalent to a GREG estimator.

4.3. Variance Estimator

Deville and Särndal (1992) proposed the variance estimator

$$\hat{V}(\hat{t}_{GREG}) = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n (\pi_{ki} - \pi_k \pi_i) (\pi_{ki})^{-1} (e_k d_k) (e_i d_i)$$

where $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$, π_k and π_{ki} are the residual, the 1st and the 2nd order inclusion probabilities respectively.

The accuracy of this variance of residuals depends on the fitting of the linear model $\hat{y}_i = (\mathbf{x}_i)' \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$. If the linear model between the current Q-Tax data and the auxiliary Q-Tax data is not appropriate, the calibrated weights may increase the variance over the HT estimator using base weights.

Deville and Särndal suggested that the calibration weights w_k should be used in the variance estimator equation above,

$$\hat{V}(\hat{t}_{GREG}) = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n (\pi_{ki} - \pi_k \pi_i) (\pi_{ki})^{-1} (e_k w_k) (e_i w_i)$$

5. Q-Tax Calibration and Standard Error Estimation

Calibration equations:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i^{yearQT} = u^{yearALFIN} \text{ for } n \text{ the sample size}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = N \text{ (the population size)}$$

where x_i^{yearQT} is the Q-Tax value of unit i and $u^{yearALFIN}$ is the ALFIN total of the same year

5.1. T09 Q-Tax Calibration from 2020 Quarter 1 (2020Q1) to 2023 Quarter 2 (2023Q2)

Table 1: CV Estimate for T09 (2020Q1-2023Q2)

Q-Tax	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
2020Q1	2.29%	0.60%	1.25%
2020Q2	6.93%	2.67%	3.39%
2020Q3	3.54%	1.90%	2.21%
2020Q4	4.44%	1.45%	1.28%
2021Q1	2.11%	0.71%	1.23%
2021Q2	5.22%	0.82%	1.19%
2021Q3	2.23%	0.75%	1.95%
2021Q4	4.56%	0.84%	1.44%
2022Q1	2.39%	0.70%	1.23%
2022Q2	4.76%	1.07%	1.27%
2022Q3	1.47%	0.61%	0.57%
2022Q4	2.05%	1.52%	1.84%
2023Q1	2.67%	1.00%	1.53%
2023Q2	2.02%	1.29%	1.31%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax 2020-2023

Figure 1: CV for T09 Estimates from 2020Q1 to 2023Q2

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax 2020-2023

The population size is $N = 9023$, the sample size is $n = 1423$, the auxiliary T09 Q-Tax years included in the model are provided in the Tables in the Appendix. Test results (See Table 1 and Figure 1) shows Raking and Linear calibrations perform better as they produce estimates with smaller coefficient of variation (CV) for Q-Tax data from the recent 14 consecutive quarters from 2020Q1 to 2023Q2.

5.2. T40 Q-Tax Calibration from 2020 Quarter 1 (2020Q1) to 2023 Quarter 2 (2023Q2)

Table 2: CV Estimate for T40 (2020Q1-2023Q2)

Q-Tax	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
2020Q1	3.49%	1.60%	1.30%
2020Q2	5.26%	2.49%	2.83%
2020Q3	5.26%	2.45%	5.22%
2020Q4	3.33%	1.50%	1.25%
2021Q1	3.46%	0.26%	0.58%
2021Q2	5.27%	0.34%	0.62%
2021Q3	3.32%	0.73%	0.79%
2021Q4	2.66%	1.01%	1.01%
2022Q1	4.44%	0.32%	0.55%
2022Q2	5.59%	0.43%	0.48%
2022Q3	4.70%	1.54%	3.40%
2022Q4	4.47%	3.98%	3.72%
2023Q1	5.65%	4.42%	4.41%
2023Q2	3.83%	2.61%	2.58%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax 2020-2023

Figure 2: CV for T40 Estimates from 2020Q1 to 2023Q2

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax 2020-2023

The population size is $N = 5041$, the sample size is $n = 357$, the auxiliary T40 Q-Tax years included in the model are provided in the Tables in the Appendix. Test results (See Table 2 and Figure 2)

show Raking and Linear calibrations perform better as they produce estimates with smaller coefficient of variation (CV) for Q-Tax data from the recent 14 consecutive quarters from 2020Q1 to 2023Q2.

5.3. T41 Q-Tax Calibration from 2020 Quarter 1 (2020Q1) to 2023 Quarter 2 (2023Q2)

Table 3: CV Estimate for T41 (2020Q1-2023Q2)

Q-Tax	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
2020Q1	1.23%	0.39%	0.05%
2020Q2	3.18%	0.32%	0.32%
2020Q3	2.61%	0.28%	0.35%
2020Q4	3.26%	0.26%	0.32%
2021Q1	0.81%	0.48%	0.37%
2021Q2	3.51%	0.19%	1.92%
2021Q3	1.69%	0.51%	0.64%
2021Q4	1.58%	0.56%	0.41%
2022Q1	0.84%	0.52%	0.41%
2022Q2	5.64%	1.33%	1.34%
2022Q3	2.53%	1.28%	10.38%
2022Q4	1.59%	0.76%	8.10%
2023Q1	3.14%	0.31%	5.42%
2023Q2	3.34%	1.05%	6.73%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax 2020-2023

Figure 3: CV for T09 Estimates from 2020Q1 to 2023Q2

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax 2020-2023

The population size is $N = 323$, the sample size is $n = 38$, the auxiliary T41 Q-Tax years included in the model are provided in the Tables in the Appendix. Test results (See Table 3 and Figure 3) shows Raking performs better than SUDAAN and SUDAAN performs better than Linear as they produce estimates with smaller coefficient of variation (CV) for Q-Tax data from the recent 14 consecutive quarters from 2020Q1 to 2023Q2.

6. Some Remarks

The new calibration R codes using raking provides better estimates compared to production program using SUDAAN. Regarding test results from using raking and linear calibration, the weights for GREG may sometimes contain negative values, and in some cases, the raking calibration for that reason is more favorable for calibrating Q-Tax data. A good indicator for selecting auxiliary data (from the years of Q-Tax being chosen in the calibration equations) is the R^2 value. So, was there a strong linear relationship between the current quarter Q-Tax data and the prior year data? A strong linear relationship provides consistent calibration for auxiliary data choices.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Khoa Dong for providing all Q-Tax data (2020Q1 to 2023Q2) ready for calibration and the calibration estimates using SUDAAN procedures. We would also like to thank all reviewers for careful readings of drafts of this paper and helpful comments.

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SUDAAN webpage: <https://sudaansupport.rti.org>

R webpage: [The Comprehensive R Archive Network \(r-project.org\)](http://TheComprehensiveRArchiveNetwork(r-project.org))

Appendix

Table A22Q4	2022 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 4		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	30,486,780	32,192,612	32,073,175
Standard Error	624,814	489,589	589,762
CV	2.05%	1.52%	1.84%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2020

Table A22Q3	2022 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 3		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	29,365,155	34,010,882	34,312,655
Standard Error	432,645	207,373	196,365
CV	1.47%	0.61%	0.57%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2020

Table A23Q2	2023 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 2		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	28,209,610	28,475,069	30,093,162
Standard Error	570,666	366,728	394,910
CV	2.02%	1.29%	1.31%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2021

Table A22Q2	2022 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 2		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	30,135,395	30,895,917	31,460,815
Standard Error	1,433,831	330,235	398,549
CV	4.76%	1.07%	1.27%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2020

Table A23Q1	2023 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 1		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
2023 Q1 Estimate	29,109,430	29,397,790	30,812,368
Standard Error	777,580	294,161	472,623
CV	2.67%	1.00%	1.53%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2021

Table A22Q1	2022 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 1		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	27,308,606	29,536,806	29,249,136
Standard Error	651,385	207,693	361,130
CV	2.39%	0.70%	1.23%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2020

Table A21Q4	2021 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 4		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	28,384,242	30,121,516	31,115,827
Standard Error	1,295,660	252,187	447,086
CV	4.56%	0.84%	1.44%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2019

Table A20Q4	2020 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 4		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	25,679,012	26,505,160	28,064,535
Standard Error	1,139,042	384,334	360,601
CV	4.44%	1.45%	1.28%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table A21Q3	2021 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 3		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	26,148,525	27,243,702	29,080,118
Standard Error	584,326	212,055	568,325
CV	2.23%	0.75%	1.95%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2019

Table A20Q3	2020 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 3		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	22,503,826	23,764,203	25,619,397
Standard Error	797,144	450,748	565,117
CV	3.54%	1.90%	2.21%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table A21Q2	2021 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 2		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	26,117,574	28,453,683	27,992,537
Standard Error	1,364,025	224,432	334,064
CV	5.22%	0.82%	1.19%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2019

Table A20Q2	2020 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 2		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	23,206,202	23,952,429	25,545,164
Standard Error	1,608,711	638,743	864,723
CV	6.93%	2.67%	3.39%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table A21Q1	2021 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 1		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	24,120,495	26,123,978	26,518,756
Standard Error	509,524	186,760	325,877
CV	2.11%	0.71%	1.23%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2019

Table A20Q1	2020 Q-Tax T09 Quarter 1		
N = 9023, n = 1423	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	23,226,355	25,580,865	25,355,756
Standard Error	531,149	154,748	316,261
CV	2.29%	0.60%	1.25%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table B22Q4	2022 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 4		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	10,550,449	10,504,382	10,913,112
Standard Error	471,731	418,404	405,643
CV	4.47%	3.98%	3.72%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017,2018,2020

Table B22Q3	2022 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 3		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	8,732,182	7,982,513	8,167,576
Standard Error	410,632	122,920	277,914
CV	4.70%	1.54%	3.40%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2020

Table B23Q2	2023 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 2		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	13,989,076	13,587,275	14,311,704
Standard Error	535,119	354,480	369,291
CV	3.83%	2.61%	2.58%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2021

Table B22Q2	2022 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 2		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	14,319,623	14,545,513	14,884,446
Standard Error	800,862	62,651	71,941
CV	5.59%	0.43%	0.48%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2019

Table B23Q1	2023 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 1		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	10,896,686	11,859,713	11,881,162
Standard Error	615,930	524,581	523,501
CV	5.65%	4.42%	4.41%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2018-2021

Table B22Q1	2022 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 1		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	11657327	11,828,231	11,956,110
Standard Error	517,436	37,889	65,478
CV	4.44%	0.32%	0.55%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2019

Table B21Q4	2021 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 4		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	9,291,988	8,896,795	8,846,399
Standard Error	247,485	90,023	89,579
CV	2.66%	1.01%	1.01%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2019

Table B20Q4	2020 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 4		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	9,060,146	10,071,709	10,309,753
Standard Error	301,800	151,471	128,499
CV	3.33%	1.50%	1.25%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table B21Q3	2021 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 3		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	8,684,832	8,096,716	8,071,430
Standard Error	288,169	58,969	63,684
CV	3.32%	0.73%	0.79%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2019

Table B20Q3	2020 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 3		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	9,604,821	9,599,723	8,507,205
Standard Error	505,357	235,002	443,716
CV	5.26%	2.45%	5.22%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table B21Q2	2021 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 2		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	13,127,691	13,393,400	13,695,017
Standard Error	692,365	45,671	85,425
CV	5.27%	0.34%	0.62%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2019

Table B20Q2	2020 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 2		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	9,247,518	9,990,203	10,114,625
Standard Error	517,734	248,540	286,333
CV	5.26%	2.49%	2.83%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table B21Q1	2021 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 1		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	10,674,178	10,597,766	10,707,245
Standard Error	369,767	27,095	62,220
CV	3.46%	0.26%	0.58%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017-2019

Table B20Q1	2020 Q-Tax T40 Quarter 1		
N = 5041, n = 357	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	9,859,503	10,049,716	10,413,456
Standard Error	344,167	160,847	135,050
CV	3.49%	1.60%	1.30%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2011-2018

Table C22Q4	2022 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 4		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,169,034	1,324,398	2,533,755
Standard Error	34,413	10,095	205,211
CV	1.59%	0.76%	8.10%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017, 2020

Table C22Q3	2022 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 3		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,132,927	1,508,614	2,980,887
Standard Error	53,899	19,237	309,534
CV	2.53%	1.28%	10.38%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017,2018,2020

Table C23Q2	2023 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 2		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	4,149,800	3,598,189	2,399,885
Standard Error	138,784	37,808	161,629
CV	3.34%	1.05%	6.73%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2019-2021

Table C22Q2	2022 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 2		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	3,437,923	3,626,860	3,628,647
Standard Error	193,908	48,306	48,547
CV	5.64%	1.33%	1.34%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017,2018,2020

Table C23Q1	2023 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 1		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	3,266,067	1,371,955	3,293,429
Standard Error	102,688	4,248	178,392
CV	3.14%	0.31%	5.42%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2019-2021

Table C22Q1	2022 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 1		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	3,311,524	3,303,316	3,316,757
Standard Error	27,739	17,261	13,435
CV	0.84%	0.52%	0.41%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017,2018,2020

Table C21Q4	2021 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 4		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,216,305	1,578,706	2,519,731
Standard Error	35,020	8,805	10,428
CV	1.58%	0.56%	0.41%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2018,2019

Table C20Q4	2020 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 4		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	1,599,838	1,563,064	1,569,662
Standard Error	52,097	4,020	5,002
CV	3.26%	0.26%	0.32%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2014,2017,2018

Table C21Q3	2021 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 3		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,194,116	2,358,388	2,785,990
Standard Error	37,105	11,954	17,726
CV	1.69%	0.51%	0.64%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2018,2019

Table C20Q3	2020 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 3		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,274,592	2,298,347	2,156,342
Standard Error	59,306	6,452	7,448
CV	2.61%	0.28%	0.35%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2012,2017,2018

Table C21Q2	2021 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 2		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	3,522,475	1,674,608	1,055,627
Standard Error	123,759	3,196	20,243
CV	3.51%	0.19%	1.92%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2018,2019

Table C20Q2	2020 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 2		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,256,710	2,259,862	2,263,209
Standard Error	71,670	7,244	7,237
CV	3.18%	0.32%	0.32%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2014,2017,2018

Table C21Q1	2021 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 1		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,604,990	2,564,621	2,581,758
Standard Error	21,137	12,349	9,505
CV	0.81%	0.48%	0.37%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2017,2018

Table C20Q1	2020 Q-Tax T41 Quarter 1		
N = 323, n = 38	Sudaan	Raking	Linear
Estimate	2,424,739	2,444,619	2,457,798
Standard Error	29,928	9,444	1,160
CV	1.23%	0.39%	0.05%

Data Source: U.S. Census Bureau Q-Tax/ ALFIN 2014,2017,2018